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pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

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Convex Leadership: Empowering Extraordinary Excellence in 2024 and Beyond

EDUARDO G. FONTILLO JR., LPT. MAT.

SHS-SCIENCE TEACHER

KAYPIAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

CSJDM/REGION 3/BULACAN/PHILIPPINES

As the idea of leadership changes, convex leadership shines as the way forward for change. While entering the world of 2024 and beyond, the overall hierarchical model does not meet the need. Convex leadership, a new approach incorporating flexibility, compassion, and anticipation of change, will undoubtedly redefine companies, motivate employees, and achieve remarkable results (*4 Critical Leadership Competencies for 2024 and Beyond*, 2024).

The Convex Mindset:

Convex leaders do not limit themselves and embrace a mindset that transcends binary thinking. It does not look at difficulties as threats to its growth but as agencies for its development. The concepts they tend to use are nonlinear; their thinking is curved. They realize that it is not a ladder that one climbs, but a set of curves, each of which ascends to a higher degree of success.

Empathy as the Core:

Indeed, empathy is the cornerstone of convex leadership. These leaders pay keen attention, comprehend the meaning of others, and seek ways of identifying with them. They understand that people are not 'assets' but complex individuals with their own abilities, weaknesses, goals, and phobias. Through this, they ensure that there is understanding between people and their physical or social surroundings, thereby promoting teamwork and creativity (Zivkovic, 2022).

Agility and Adaptability:

Convex leaders are great adapters. They adapt to floating change agents that are blowing. They do not reply to rock-solid strategies, which are more troublesome in a time of uncertainty; they adapt. These individuals can readily identify new trends, opportunities, and threats, articulate ways to manage change, and lead other people through unpredictable situations.

Visionary Decision-Making:

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Convex leaders do not act in ways that only bring win-win solutions in the short term. These people wake up, look at the horizon, and dream of a future that is beyond it. When making these choices, they do not prioritize fortune, morality, or the effectiveness of their endeavors but the good they wish to bring in the long run. It vicariously resolves the conflict between self-fulfillment in the present and the establishment of a lasting legacy.

Amplifying Collective Intelligence:

Rather than relying solely on their brilliance and believing that leaders must possess exceptional intelligence, Convex leaders harness the employees' collective wisdom. They bring in different ideas; they create a culture of openness where people don't feel embarrassed to share ideas; and they bring ideas to interaction and transformation. Thus, they rely on synergy; that is, the properties of the whole are greater than the properties of each of the components that compose it.

Convex leadership is not a process; it is an attitude or approach, namely, bending the angles of orthodoxy, cherishing the manifold, and motivating others to succeed. Now, as we embark on the future, it is high time that this convex mindset be embraced so much into the future discovery and the reality of extraordinary excellence achieved one curve at a time.

References

Zivkovic, S. (2022). Empathy in Leadership: How it Enhances Effectiveness. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361952690_Empathy_in_Leadership_How_it_Enhances_Effectiveness

4 Critical leadership competencies for 2024 and beyond. (2024, February 26). 4 Critical Leadership Competencies for 2024 and Beyond. <https://insights.transearch.com/2024/02/26/4-critical-leadership-competencies-for-2024-and-beyond/>

Clark, L. (2018, December 19). *Navigating Complexity: A new map for a new territory*. Harvard Business Publishing. <https://www.harvardbusiness.org/navigating-complexity-a-new-map-for-a-new-territory/>

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